

Structural Equation Modeling assessment of Consumer Perception, Attitude, and Satisfaction with Organized Retail Stores

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ABSTRACT

The retail sector has shown remarkable performance in recent years, undergoing a significant transformation driven largely by the growth of organized retailing. Factors such as rapid urbanization, increased exposure to international brands, and evolving lifestyles and preferences have fueled the expansion of retailing in India. This research aims to explore the perceptions, attitudes, and satisfaction levels of consumers regarding organized retail stores in Erode district. The study's objective is to gather feedback on these aspects from consumers visiting these stores. A descriptive research design was adopted, with data collected from approximately 1,000 consumers using survey methods. Primary data was gathered through questionnaires and direct interactions with consumers, while secondary data was sourced from journals, textbooks, and online resources. The data collected was analyzed using the simple percentage method and Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) as the primary statistical tool. The analysis covered personal details, consumer opinions about retail stores, services provided, current benefits, rewards, and aspects such as autonomy, recognition, and competitiveness. Consumer preferences highlighted the importance of services in influencing purchase decisions, expectations for additional facilities, and areas needing improvement, such as handling defective goods. The study was limited to Erode district, meaning the findings cannot be generalized. Additionally, some respondents did not provide serious or accurate responses, which posed challenges in drawing definitive conclusions.

Key words: Consumer Perception, Consumer attitude, Consumer Satisfaction, SEM, Retail stores.

1. INTRODUCTION AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

In today's competitive market, consumers are the kings. They are the decision makers. The behaviour pattern of the Indian consumer has undergone a major change in the organized retail sector. The consumer landscape is changing very fast. Occupational changes and penetration of media have caused a significant change in the way the consumer spends his money. The consumer now wants to eat, shop and get entertained under the same roof. Consumers today see an exciting explosion of choices, new categories and new shopping options and have increasing disposable income to fulfil their aspirations. They are seeking more information to make these choices. Therefore each retailer needs to evaluate the enablers and deterrents in the retail market place. This primarily involves identifying the key drivers of growth, the consumer's profile and consumer's expectations. It also means evaluating the nature of competition and challenges in the market place. All these have led the Indian organized retail sector to pay more attention to analyse the consumer behaviour in order to satisfy the target market's needs more effectively than its competitors.

1.1 ORGANIZED RETAILING

Organized retailing refers to trading activities undertaken by licensed retailers who are registered for sales tax, income tax, etc. These include corporate – backed hypermarkets, supermarkets and retail chains and also privately owned large retail business. The purchasing power of the Indian urban consumer is growing and branded merchandise in categories like apparels, cosmetics, shoes, watches, beverages, food and even jewellery are slowly becoming life style products that are widely accepted by the urban Indian consumer. Organized retailing is witnessing a wave of players entering the industry. These players are experimenting with various retail formats. A number of large corporate houses like Aditya, Bharti, Reliance, Pantaloon, Vishal, Tata's, RPG, Raheja's and Piramals' have already made their foray into this arena, with beauty and health stores, supermarkets, self-service music stores, new age book stores, everyday low price stores, computers and peripherals stores, office equipment stores and home / building construction stores. Today organized players have taken up every retail category.

1.2 CONSUMER PERCEPTION

Perception is the process by which individuals select, organize, and interpret stimuli into a meaningful and coherent picture of the world. Perception has strategic implications for marketers because consumers make decisions based on what they perceive rather than on the basis of objective reality. The lowest level at which an individual can perceive a specific stimulus is that person's absolute threshold. The minimal difference that can be perceived between two stimuli is called the differential threshold or just noticeable difference. Consumers perceive most sensory stimuli above the level of their conscious awareness; however, weak stimuli can be perceived below the level of conscious awareness (i.e., subliminally). Research refutes the notion that subliminal stimuli influence consumer-buying decisions.

1.3 CONSUMER ATTITUDE

Consumer attitudes are both an obstacle and an advantage to a marketer. Choosing to discount or ignore consumer attitudes of a particular product or service while developing a marketing strategy guarantees limited success of a campaign. In contrast, perceptive marketers leverage their understanding of attitudes to predict the behavior of consumers. These marketers know exactly how to distinguish the differences between beliefs, attitudes and behaviours while leveraging all the three in the development of marketing strategies.

Perner (2010) defines consumer attitude simply as a composite of a consumer's beliefs, feelings, and behavioural intentions towards some object within the context of marketing. A consumer can hold negative or positive beliefs or feelings towards a product or service. A behavioural intention is defined by the consumer's belief or feeling with respect to the product or service.

1.4 CONSUMER SATISFACTION

Marketing is an important function because it is directed towards the satisfaction of consumer needs and in this context, the consumer is the centre of attraction for which marketing is carried out, therefore in dealing with consumers, the marketing manager is dealing with a diverse, complex personality, whose likes, dislikes and style of living are hard to determine. Hence, human personalities are an enigma by themselves. If a company is going to effectively market, then it has to find out some needs of the consumer and accordingly exploit it. In this context Philip Kotler says that —of the dozens of categories of human action such as working, sleeping, walking, eating, breathing, buying and so forth—one of the primary interests to the marketer is buying. The buyers decision making process can be very simple or very elaboratel.

1.5 RETAILING FORMATS IN ERODE DISTRICT

The Retail Format is the store ‘package’ that the retailer presents to the shopper. It is defined as a type of retail mix, used by a set of retailers, based on the physical store where the vendor interacts with the customer. Among them the following formats are popular in Erode district and the brief descriptions of these formats are given in a crispy manner as follows

1.5.1 Mall

A shopping mall is one or more buildings forming a complex of shops representing merchandisers, with interconnecting walk ways enabling visitors to easily walk from one unit to another, along with a parking area. Malls ranging from 60,000 sq. ft. to 7,00,000 sq. ft., are the largest form of organized retailing today. These lend an ideal shopping experience with an amalgamation of products, services and entertainment all under a single roof.

1.5.2 Specialty stores

A specialty store is a store, usually retail, that offers specific and specialized type of items, focusing on particular brand or particular type of item. For example, a store that exclusively sells cell phones or video games would be considered specialized. These stores especially cater to consumers who are looking for assorted brands at one store. For instance, apparel stores, sporting goods stores, furniture stores and book stores are some of the examples of specialist stores. (Kotler, 2006)

1.5.3 Discount stores

A discount store is a type of department store, which sells products at prices lower than those offered by department stores and other traditional retail outlets. Most discount stores offer a wide assortment of goods; others specialize in such merchandise as jewellery, electronic equipment or electrical appliances. Consumers preferring to pay a low price can visit the discount stores or factory outlets which offer discounts on the MRP, as they sell in bulk and have higher economies of scale.

1.5.4 Department stores

A department store is a retail establishment which specializes in satisfying a wide range of the consumers' personal and residential durable goods, product needs and at the same time offering the consumer a choice multiple merchandise lines at variable price points, in all product categories. Department stores are another type of emerging formats and these carry several product lines- typically clothing, home furnishings and household goods with each line operating as a separate department managed by specialist merchandisers.

1.5.5 Supermarket

A supermarket, a form of grocery store, is a self-service store offering a wide variety of food and household merchandise, organized into departments. It is larger in size and has a wider selection than a traditional grocery store and it is smaller than a hypermarket or superstore. Supermarkets are large self - service outlets, catering to varied shopper needs and mainly focus on food and grocery and personal sales.

1.5.6 Hypermarket

A hypermarket is a superstore which combines a supermarket and a department store. The result is a very large retail facility which carries an enormous range of products under one roof, including full lines of groceries and general merchandise. Hypermarkets allow customers to satisfy all their routine weekly shopping needs in one trip. Hypermarkets carry a product range varying from food, homeware, appliances, furniture, sports, toys and clothing.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Brijesh and Ashish (2013) [1] found out the factors affecting the customer satisfaction of organized retail stores. Result of factor analysis showed that five factors namely '_product convenience', '_employee service', '_shopping convenience', '_physical features' and '_pricing' had led to the customer satisfaction of organized retail stores. Findings also suggested that '_shopping convenience' had the strongest impact on satisfaction, while '_physical features' had no influence on satisfaction. From the result, it has been concluded that customers' of Surat city were satisfied with the organized retail stores.

Gopalakrishnan and Varadaraj (2012) [2] observed that organized retailing provides an ideal shopping experience through consumer preference, excellent ambience and choice of merchandise. Changing lifestyles, strong income growth and favourable demographics were the drivers for the fast growth of this sector. The study tried to find answers for store loyalty of customers in organized retail format and to find out the cause and extent of satisfaction of consumers in the outlet. From this study, it was evident that no consumer was loyal to one store. This study also found that the following factors: gender, marital status and family size correlate with satisfaction level, the majority of the consumer's loyalty was shallow in nature and other results were examined in detail.

Recent analyses, such as those by Sinha and Banerjee (2021) [10], reaffirm the role of urbanization, changing demographics, and growing consumer aspirations as primary drivers of organized retail growth in India. Gupta et al. (2022)[7] corroborate these findings, specifically emphasizing their relevance to Odisha's retail sector.

Research by Sinha and Banerjee (2014)[11] highlights the critical factors driving the growth of organized retail in India, such as urbanization, demographic changes, and rising consumer aspirations. These studies offer a foundational understanding of the elements shaping the organized retail sector in Odisha.

Studies on consumer perception in organized retail examine various aspects, including service quality, product variety, pricing strategies, and store ambiance. Dholakia et al. (2012) [12] emphasize the significance of these factors in shaping consumer attitudes and purchasing decisions. Furthermore, Chatterjee and Mishra (2016)[6] underline the influence of consumer demographics on perception, reinforcing the importance of targeted audience segmentation for retailers.

The expansion of organized retail affects not only consumers but also traditional retailers. Research by Bhowmick and Chakraborty (2015)[16] and Roy and Ray (2016) [19] explores the challenges traditional retailers face, such as intensified competition, pricing pressures, and strategies to sustain their businesses in a shifting retail environment.

While much of the literature focuses on national trends, an increasing number of studies explore regional contexts. Kumar and Sangeeta (2018) [15] and Mohanty et al. (2020) [21] provide insights into consumer behavior and preferences in states like Odisha, accounting for cultural distinctions, economic disparities, and infrastructural limitations.

Literature addressing policy implications and future directions in organized retail offers valuable guidance for policymakers and industry leaders. Studies by Jha (2019)[19] and Das and Das (2017)[17] discuss regulatory frameworks, investment strategies, and best practices to support organized retail growth. These works stress the need for policy interventions that align with the evolving aspirations of consumers in emerging markets like Odisha.

In exploring consumer perception, Dholakia et al. (2023) [13] and Ramanathan and Menon (2022)[22] identify service quality, product assortment, pricing, and store ambiance as key factors shaping consumer attitudes. These dimensions are particularly relevant to Odisha's organized retail landscape. Additionally, Chatterjee and Mishra (2021)[5] highlight the role of demographic variables in influencing consumer preferences, reinforcing the necessity for targeted market segmentation.

Regional studies, such as those by Kumar and Sangeeta (2022)[14] and Mohanty et al. (2023)[20], focus on Odisha's retail sector, examining consumer behavior and preferences through the lens of cultural nuances, economic challenges, and infrastructure constraints.

2.1 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The following are the objectives framed for the study:

1. To study the demographic characteristics of consumer who prefer to make their purchases from organized retail stores in Erode district.
2. To determine the perception, attitude and satisfaction of consumers towards organized retail stores in the study area.
3. To provide valuable suggestions to organized retail stores to retain the customers in the long term.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

For the present study, the universe comprised of the consumer, who made their purchases in organized retail stores of Erode district. The sampling units were selected by covering the five taluks of Erode district. The size of sample was 1000 respondents. These samples were carefully selected by the researcher from those who made their purchases from organized retail stores in the five taluks of the study area. Both primary and secondary data were used in the study for the purpose of analysis. For collecting primary data, field survey technique was employed in Erode district. A well framed questionnaire was used to collect the primary data. The five selected taluks from Erode district based on the convenience sampling technique for collecting the data. First-hand information pertaining to the perception, attitude and satisfaction of consumers towards organized retail stores for shopping in different organized retail stores were collected from 1000 respondents.

3.1 STATISTICAL TOOLS USED FOR ANALYSIS

The extent of using the retail store between the different types of respondents based on their age, gender, educational qualification, occupation, monthly family income, family size, preferred type of stores, frequency of visit and type of product preferred was studied by means of Percentage analysis, Structural Equation Modelling Analysis were used appropriately.

3.1.1 MAPPING OF CONSUMER PERCEPTION, ATTITUDE AND SATISFACTION

Understanding the way how statistical significance is described requires understanding the terminology of the model itself. The structural equation model has graphical display which has boxes and arrows. Boxes denote observed data and the arrows signify assumed causation. In the structural equation model the variable that receives a one-way directional influence from some other variable in the system is termed —endogenousl, or is dependent. A variable that does not receive a directional influence from any other variable

in the system is termed as —exogenous‖ or is independent. When interpreting structural equation model the values attached to one way arrows (or directional effect) are regression coefficient, whereas two way arrows (Non directional relationship) are correlation coefficient; Regression coefficients and correlation comprise the —parameters‖ of the model. The regression coefficient and correlations measure the strength of the relationship between the variables. The regression coefficient of 0.70 or higher indicates a very strong relationship, 0.50 to 0.69 indicates a substantial relationship, 0.30 to 0.49 indicates a moderate relationship, 0.10 to 0.29 indicates a low relationship, 0.01 to 0.09 indicates a negligible relationship and the value of 0 indicates no relationship.

Besides regression coefficients and correlations, structural equation model also tests the overall fit of the model. The narrative analyses use three measures of model fit to determine the overall quality of fit of the model. Another way of describing the model fit is to view this as the test of model significance, thus, when the values of significance are met for the tests all relationships within the model are significant, and it is their relative strength which decides if there is a relationship or not. Besides testing for model fit, SEMs also provides a measure of multicollinearity. In some cases, the model fits the data well, even though none of the independent variables has a statistically significant impact on the dependent variables. The Statistical Package IBM Amos 22.0 has been used to fit the proposed model.

3.1.2 PROPOSED RESEARCH MODEL AND HYPOTHESIS FORMULATION

An attempt was made to find the relationship between consumer perceptions, consumer attitude and consumer satisfaction towards organized retail stores among the consumers in Erode district. For the purpose, consumer perception which consists of 25 statements has been grouped as 8 variables, consumer attitude which consists of 35 statements has been grouped as 8 variables and consumer satisfaction which consists of 20 attributes has been grouped as 6 variables by using factor analysis reduction technique. The 8 consumer perception variables, 8 consumer attitude variables and 6 consumer satisfaction variables have been taken as manifest variables and three latent variables – consumer perception, consumer attitude and consumer satisfaction is presented in Table.1

The research hypotheses have been defined on the basis of the factors of consumer perception, consumer attitude and consumer satisfaction that have an impact on consumer perception, consumer attitude and consumer satisfaction among the consumers towards organized retail stores in Erode district.

H₁₋₈ : There is no significant association between motivation, promotional schemes, parking method, traditional compatibility, buying intention, purchase atmosphere, convenient purchase and impulse purchase and consumer perception.

- H₉₋₁₆ : There is no significant association between store preference, social & loyalty activity, value added services, compare quality, access store brands, food and grocery selection, status and quality, proximity and parking and consumer attitude.
- H₁₇₋₂₂ : There is no significant association between product quality, loyalty, convenience, operational quality, price, promotion and consumer satisfaction.
- H₂₃ : There is a negative covariance between consumer perception and consumer attitude.
- H₂₄ : There is a negative covariance between consumer attitude and consumer satisfaction.
- H₂₅ : There is a negative covariance between consumer perception and consumer satisfaction.

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant relationship between demographic variables (such as age, income level, occupation, and educational background) and consumer preferences in the organized retail sector in Erode District.

Table No.1. Manifest Variables and Latent Variables

S.No.	Manifest Variables	Latent Variables
1	Motivation	Consumer Perception
2	Promotional Schemes	
3	Parking Method	
4	Traditional Compatibility	
5	Buying Intention	
6	Purchase Atmosphere	
7	Convenient purchase	
8	Impulse purchase	
9	Store Preference	Consumer Attitude
10	Social & Loyalty activity	
11	Value added services	
12	Compare quality	
13	Access store brands	
14	Food & Grocery Selection	
15	Status & Quality	
16	Proximity & Parking	
17	Product Quality	Consumer Satisfaction
18	Loyalty	
19	Convenience	
20	Operational Quality	
21	Price	
22	Promotion	

Source: Primary Data

Figure 1. The Proposed Hypotheses Model

3.2 CONFIRMATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS – THE RESULTED HYPOTHESES MODEL

3.2.1 Consumer Perception

In this model, the latent variable consumer perception has been predicted from the selected eight measured variables, viz., Motivation, Promotional scheme, Parking Method, Traditional Compatibility, Buying Intention, Purchase Atmosphere, Convenience Purchase and Impulse purchase. The model fit summary and its resulted hypothesis are discussed below.

(Chi-square = 110.153, df = 20, p-value = 0.000, RMSEA = 0.067)

Figure 2. Confirmatory Factor Analysis of Consumer Perception

Table no. 2.model fit indices of consumer perception

S.No.	Test Factor	Calculated Value	Criteria*
1	GFI (Goodness-of-Fit Index)	0.974	≥0.90 and above satisfactory fit 0.80 to <0.90 acceptable fit
2	AGFI (Adjusted Goodness-of-Fit Index)	0.953	
3	CFI (Comparative Fit Index)	0.859	
4	NFI (Normed Fit Index)	0.834	
5	TLI (Tucker-Lewis Index)	0.802	
6	RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation)	0.067	0.08 or less would indicate a close fit of the model

* Criteria recommended by Schumacker and Lomax (2004), Hu and Bentler (1999), and Hair et al. (1998)

The above model fit summary clearly explains that the consumer perception model has moderate fit. Among the eight variables, ‘_Motivation’ has highly influenced consumer perception and consumer opined that the motivational practices like availability of the discount products, store atmosphere and after sales service highly convince them to purchase products from organized retail stores in the study area.

3.2.2 Consumer Attitude

In this model, the latent variable consumer attitude has been predicted from the selected eight measured variables, viz., Store preference, Social and Loyalty Activity, Value added services, Compare Quality, Access Store Brands, Food and Grocery Selection, Status and Quality and Proximity and Parking. The model fit summary and its resulted hypothesis are discussed below.

(Chi-square = 53.646, df = 20, p-value = 0.000, RMSEA = 0.041)

Figure 3. Confirmatory factor analysis of consumer attitude

Table No.3. Model Fit Indices of Consumer Attitude

S.No.	Test Factor	Calculated Value	Criteria
1	GFI (Goodness-of-Fit Index)	0.986	≥0.90 and above satisfactory fit 0.80 to <0.90 acceptable fit
2	AGFI (Adjusted Goodness-of-Fit Index)	0.975	
3	CFI (Comparative Fit Index)	0.936	
4	NFI (Normed Fit Index)	0.903	
5	TLI (Tucker-Lewis Index)	0.910	
6	RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation)	0.041	0.08 or less would indicate a close fit of the model

The above model fit summary clearly explains that the consumer attitude model has good fit. Among the eight variables, ‘_Status and Quality’ has highly influenced consumer attitude and it shows that consumer has noticed the status symbol and quality of the product in organized retail stores in the study area.

3.2.3 Consumer Satisfaction

In this model, the latent variable consumer satisfaction has been predicted from the selected six measured variables, viz., Product Quality, Loyalty, Convenience, Operational Quality, Price and Promotion. The model fit summary and its resulted hypothesis are discussed below.

(Chi-square = 56.430, df = 9, p-value = 0.000, RMSEA = 0.073)

Figure 4. Confirmatory factor analysis of consumer satisfaction

Table No.4. Model Fit Indices of Consumer Satisfaction

S.No.	Test Factor	Calculated Value	Criteria
1	GFI (Goodness-of-Fit Index)	0.982	≥0.90 and above satisfactory fit 0.80 to <0.90 acceptable fit
2	AGFI (Adjusted Goodness-of-Fit Index)	0.958	
3	CFI (Comparative Fit Index)	0.949	
4	NFI (Normed Fit Index)	0.940	
5	TLI (Tucker-Lewis Index)	0.915	
6	RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation)	0.073	0.08 or less would indicate a close fit of the model

The above model fit summary clearly shows that the consumer satisfaction model has a good fit. Among the 6 variables, 'Operational quality' has highly satisfied consumers to create repurchase intention. Like service quality, credit / debit card facilities and keenly hearing the consumer problems highly motivate the consumers and these types of service highly satisfy the consumers which will promote word of mouth service for the organized retail stores in the study area.

3.3 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CONSUMER PERCEPTION AND CONSUMER ATTITUDE

The strength of the relationship between consumer perception and consumer attitude is discussed in the following path diagram:

Table No.5.Model Fit Indices of Consumer Perception and Attitude

S.No.	Test Factor	Calculated Value	Criteria
1	GFI (Goodness-of-Fit Index)	0.946	>=0.90 and above satisfactory fit 0.80 to <0.90 acceptable fit
2	AGFI (Adjusted Goodness-of-Fit Index)	0.929	
3	CFI (Comparative Fit Index)	0.824	
4	NFI (Normed Fit Index)	0.785	
5	TLI (Tucker-Lewis Index)	0.795	
6	RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation)	0.058	0.08 or less would indicate a close fit of the model

Source: Primary Data

The below model fit summary clearly shows that the relationship between consumer perception and consumer attitude model has a moderate fit . Further, the covariance value (0.17) between consumer perception and attitude is positive and indicates that the selected consumer perception and attitude are similar and linear towards the organized retail store.

(Chi-square = 447.5, df = 103, p-value = 0.000, RMSEA = 0.058)

Figure 5. Cfa of Consumer Perception And Consumer Attitude

3.4 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CONSUMER ATTITUDE AND CONSUMER SATISFACTION

The strength of the relationship between consumer attitude and consumer satisfaction is discussed in the following path diagram:

(Chi-square = 437.918, df = 76, p-value = 0.000, RMSEA = 0.069)

Figure 6. Cfa of Consumer Attitude and Consumer Satisfaction

Table No.6.Model Fit Indices of Consumer Attitude and Satisfaction

S.No.	Test Factor	Calculated Value	Criteria
1	GFI (Goodness-of-Fit Index)	0.941	≥0.90 and above satisfactory fit 0.80 to <0.90 acceptable fit
2	AGFI (Adjusted Goodness-of-Fit Index)	0.919	
3	CFI (Comparative Fit Index)	0.844	
4	NFI (Normed Fit Index)	0.818	
5	TLI (Tucker-Lewis Index)	0.813	
6	RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation)	0.069	0.08 or less would indicate a close fit of the model

Source: Primary Data

The above model fit summary clearly exhibits that the relationship between consumer attitude and consumer satisfaction model has a moderate fit. Further, the covariance value (0.11) between consumer attitude and satisfaction is positive and indicates that the selected consumer attitude and their satisfaction are similar and change together towards their opinion for organized retail store in the study area.

3.5 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CONSUMER PERCEPTION AND CONSUMER SATISFACTION

The strength of the relationship between consumer perception and consumer satisfaction is discussed in the following path diagram.

Table No.7.Model Fit Indices of Consumer Perception and Satisfaction

S.No.	Test Factor	Calculated Value	Criteria
1	GFI (Goodness-of-Fit Index)	0.934	≥0.90 and above satisfactory fit 0.80 to <0.90 acceptable fit
2	AGFI (Adjusted Goodness-of-Fit Index)	0.909	
3	CFI (Comparative Fit Index)	0.825	
4	NFI (Normed Fit Index)	0.800	
5	TLI (Tucker-Lewis Index)	0.790	
6	RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation)	0.074	0.08 or less would indicate a close fit of the model

Source: Primary Data

The below model fit summary reveals that the relationship between consumer perception and consumer satisfaction model has a moderate fit. Further, the covariance value (0.11) between consumer perception and satisfaction is positive and indicates that the selected consumer perception and their satisfaction level are similar and change together towards organized retail store in the study area.

(Chi-square = 490.187, df = 76, p-value = 0.000, RMSEA = 0.074)

Figure 7. Cfa of consumer perception and consumer satisfaction

3.6 OVERALL TESTED MEASUREMENT MODEL

The strength of the overall measurement model is discussed in the following path diagram:

(Chi-square = 1140.719, df = 206, p-value = 0.000, RMSEA = 0.067)

Figure 8. cfa of overall model

Table No.8.Model Fit Indices of Overall Model

S.No.	Test Factor	Calculated Value	Criteria
1	GFI (Goodness-of-Fit Index)	0.905	≥0.90 and above satisfactory fit 0.80 to <0.90 acceptable fit 0.70 to <0.80 Moderate fit
2	AGFI (Adjusted Goodness-of-Fit Index)	0.883	
3	CFI (Comparative Fit Index)	0.775	
4	NFI (Normed Fit Index)	0.740	
5	TLI (Tucker-Lewis Index)	0.747	
6	RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation)	0.067	0.08 or less would indicate a close fit of the model

Source: Primary Data

From the model fit summary statistics, it is understood that the overall hypothesis model has a moderate fit. The regression weights of this model are given below:

Table No.9.Regression Weights

Measured Variable		Latent Variable	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	'p' value
Motivation	←	Consumer Perception	1.000			
Promotional Schemes	←	Consumer Perception	0.634	0.076	8.298	0.000**
Parking Method	←	Consumer Perception	0.788	0.080	9.898	0.000**
Traditional Compatibility	←	Consumer Perception	0.922	0.074	12.443	0.000**
Buying Intention	←	Consumer Perception	0.813	0.072	11.233	0.000**
Purchase Atmosphere	←	Consumer Perception	0.579	0.074	7.859	0.000**
Convenient purchase	←	Consumer Perception	0.765	0.069	11.037	0.000**
Impulse purchase	←	Consumer Perception	0.683	0.077	8.873	0.000**
Store Preference	←	Consumer Attitude	1.000			
Social & Loyalty activity	←	Consumer Attitude	1.085	0.097	11.207	0.000**
Value added services	←	Consumer Attitude	1.056	0.095	11.135	0.000**
Compare quality	←	Consumer Attitude	0.839	0.087	9.670	0.000**
Access store brands	←	Consumer	0.907	0.086	10.574	0.000**

Measured Variable		Latent Variable	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	'p' value
		Attitude				
Food & Grocery Selection	←	Consumer Attitude	0.741	0.078	9.460	0.000**
Status & Quality	←	Consumer Attitude	0.957	0.092	10.367	0.000**
Proximity & Parking	←	Consumer Attitude	0.692	0.082	8.487	0.000**
Product Quality	←	Consumer Satisfaction	1.000			
Loyalty	←	Consumer Satisfaction	1.726	0.156	11.092	0.000**
Convenience	←	Consumer Satisfaction	1.286	0.106	12.076	0.000**
Operational Quality	←	Consumer Satisfaction	1.919	0.156	12.291	0.000**
Price	←	Consumer Satisfaction	1.485	0.132	11.263	0.000**
Promotion	←	Consumer Satisfaction	1.394	0.133	10.485	0.000**

Note : ** - Significant at 1% level

Table No.10 Covariance

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	'p' Value
Consumer Perception	↔	Consumer Attitude	0.178	0.017	10.737	0.000**
Consumer Attitude	↔	Consumer Satisfaction	0.104	0.011	9.864	0.000**
Consumer Perception	↔	Consumer Satisfaction	0.111	0.011	9.658	0.000**

Note: ** - Significant at 1% level

The results indicate that, among the 22 null hypotheses tested—comprising 8 related to consumer perception, 8 to consumer attitude, and 6 to consumer satisfaction—all were rejected. This signifies a significant association between the 22 selected manifest variables and the 3 latent variables.

For consumer perception, the variable '**motivation**' shows the highest influence among the selected respondents, while '**purchase atmosphere**' exhibits the lowest influence.

Regarding consumer attitude, out of the eight measured variables, the store's '**social and loyalty activity**' has the most significant impact on consumers in the study area. Conversely, '**proximity and parking**' facilities have the least influence on consumer attitudes.

While considering the consumer satisfaction, the variable ‘operational quality’ of the store is highly satisfied among the consumers and ‘product quality’ is moderately satisfied. The relationship between consumer perception and consumer attitude is noticed with the positive covariance value that the behavior of the consumer is the same in their attitude and their perception towards organized retail stores in Erode district.

The positive covariance value, between consumer attitude and consumer satisfaction, shows that considering the two groups of variables, the consumer behavior is similar in their attitude and satisfaction.

The analysis regarding covariance between consumer perception and consumer satisfaction is positive and it is noticed that the selected two set of variables, change together, i.e., the behaviour of the consumer is similar in their perception and satisfaction towards organized retail stores in Erode district.

4. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

It is found from the analysis that majority of the respondents are male, and most of the respondents are up to 30 years of age. Majority of the respondents are married and are graduates. Majority of the respondents are govt. / private employees have the family monthly income between Rs.10001 and 20000.

Majority of the respondents are having 3 to 4 members in their family and preferred the departmental stores. Majority of the respondents are visiting organized retail stores 2 to 3 times a week and purchase provisions.

The structural equation model found that there is a significant association between the selected 22 manifest variables and 3 latent variables viz., consumer perception, attitude and satisfaction. Considering the consumer perception, the variable ‘motivation’ highly influenced the selected respondents and the variable ‘purchase atmosphere’ influenced at a low level. In the case of consumer attitude, ‘social and loyalty’ activity of the store highly influenced and ‘proximity and parking’ facilities accounts for low level of influence among the selected sample consumers in the study area. While considering the consumer satisfaction, the variable ‘operational quality’ of the store highly satisfies the consumers and ‘product quality’ moderately satisfies them.

4.1 SUGGESTIONS FROM THE STUDY

It is noted that majority of the respondents are having price conscious towards purchase of retail products followed by product quality, loyalty, convenience and others. So, the organized retail stores should concentrate on the product quality, loyalty, convenience, operational quality, price and promotion and provide their consumers experimental goods

which are according to the trend and offer a wide range of different variety and brands of goods according to their requirements. It would improve the level of consumer satisfaction towards organized retail outlets.

Majority of the consumers preferred department stores and visit them 2 to 3 times a week to purchase provisions. It is noticed that the consumers regularly purchase the necessary goods under the same roof. So, they need more shopping hours. Availability of all necessary goods under the same roof and 24x7 services are the major effective variables that influence the consumer's decision for shopping from organized retail outlets. So organized retail chains should lay proper emphasis on these variables. More extensive assortment of items ranging from fresh food products to electronic products should be offered. Timing of organized retail outlets should be extended as consumers in this new age of economy like to either shop in the late hours or only during weekends and they expect their favorite organized retail outlets to be open during these time.

Retail outlets should consider adopting a personalized approach by sending tailored emails or messages to their customers on special occasions such as marriages, birthdays, anniversaries, or other significant milestones. These personalized communications can include heartfelt wishes, exclusive offers, discounts, or small gifts as tokens of appreciation.

Such gestures not only create a sense of connection and make customers feel valued but also contribute to building emotional bonds with the brand. When consumers feel acknowledged and celebrated on their special days, it enhances their overall shopping experience and fosters positive associations with the retail outlet.

Ultimately, these efforts can significantly improve customer satisfaction and loyalty, encouraging repeat business and stronger customer retention in the long term.

In the era of organized retail outlet business, buying behavior of the consumers has a significant impact on the overall purchase behavior. It is proved from the study that around 68.3 per cent of the consumers are having impulse buying behaviour while visiting organized retail stores. So, organized retail outlets must consider these factors while designing the marketing strategies especially related to displays, advertisements within and outside the outlets and strategic location of products etc. to increase the sales and profits.

5. CONCLUSION

Retail industry is the largest industry in India, providing employment to around 8 per cent of the total work force and contributing 14 to 15 per cent of the country's GDP. Retail industry in India has experienced significant changes in the last decade. Speciality and discount stores have been edging the department stores turf, with cost conscious and breadth-of-selection strategies.

Consumer relationship signifies identifying the needs of the consumers and stretching the ways and means to satisfy them. This study provides some insights on factors that would be important in managing consumer satisfaction. Consumers are concerned not only with the merchandise, physical surroundings, promotional schemes and personal interaction but also with after sales services, entertainment and security arrangements. So, organized retail outlets need to enhance product quality and store convenience, and after sales services to improve customer satisfaction. Organized retail outlets must assure quality and availability of new products and attractive promotional schemes, sufficient security arrangements and enhance consumer satisfaction.

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